

IMPROVING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF PRACTICAL EDUCATION THROUGH ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

Ashurova Zulaykho Erkinovna

Independent researcher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14352327>

Annotation: This article discusses the theoretical and practical aspects of developing intercultural communication skills of students of applied education in the process of teaching English. Effective methods and approaches are proposed to develop intercultural communication competence by increasing students' understanding of cultural diversity, forming in them respect and interest in the cultures of other peoples. The author presents his recommendations for improving intercultural communication among students through the use of modern technologies, project-based learning and interactive methods in English lessons.

Keywords: Intercultural communication, English teaching, applied education, language competence, cultural diversity, interactive methods, modern pedagogical technologies, project-based learning.

Introduction:

In today's globalized world, knowledge of a foreign language is not only a means of communication, but also an important key to intercultural communication. Since English has become an international language of communication, its study and effective use have become a responsible task. However, the essence of language learning is not limited to knowledge of grammatical rules and vocabulary. It also includes understanding the culture of other peoples, respecting their customs and traditions, and developing the ability to cooperate with representatives of different nationalities.

Intercultural communication is considered a decisive factor in maintaining peace and stability in the world today. Therefore, preparing students of applied sciences in this regard and turning them into mature specialists with intercultural communication skills is one of the main goals of modern education. Teaching English serves as an excellent platform for achieving this goal.

In this article, we will learn about the importance of developing intercultural communication skills in the process of teaching English, and how effective methods and approaches can help in this regard. This is an issue that should be in the focus of attention not only of academic teachers, but also of everyone who communicates in foreign languages in practical life.

Methodology:

Developing intercultural communication skills is a complex but interesting task that requires moving away from traditional approaches in the educational process and actively forming students' communication skills. The choice of methods in ensuring intercultural communication in teaching English is of paramount importance. After all, each method should allow students to exchange ideas, increase their enthusiasm for learning other cultures, and expand the opportunity to share their cultural heritage.

One of the main approaches in this process is the project-based teaching methodology. Preparing projects for students in English, for example, studying cultural festivals of other countries or preparing presentations on the topic of international friendship, serves to build intercultural bridges between them. This not only helps to learn the language, but also forms an understanding of the values of other nations and a respectful approach to them.

Role-playing and dialogue-based exercises are also effective tools for developing intercultural communication. Students' ability to imagine themselves as representatives of another nationality and solve problems related to a particular culture develops their empathy skills. Through these exercises, not only language skills are formed, but also soft skills necessary for international communication. The use of modern technologies within the methodology is also important. Information and communication technologies, in particular, the ability to conduct online discussions with peers abroad through virtual communication platforms, introduce students to a real intercultural environment. Through this experience, students not only learn to communicate in English, but also acquire the skills to work effectively in an international team.

The success of each method in developing intercultural communication depends on the environment created for students. The teacher, first of all, must create an open, respectful and interesting classroom atmosphere. Only then will the learning process become for students not only a process of acquiring knowledge, but also a process of expanding cultural thinking.

Discussion:

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of intercultural communication in today's world. Developing this competency in the process of teaching English serves not only to help students master the grammar and vocabulary of a foreign language, but also to form them as global citizens. However, this process also involves a number of problems and difficulties, which require deep reflection.

The first issue is the level of motivation among students. Each student has a different interest and readiness for intercultural communication. Some are eager

to learn new cultures, while others may not consider this topic to be very important. The teacher's task here is to identify the specific needs of each student and find motivational factors for them. For example, students can be interested in engaging in practical conversations with representatives of other nationalities, showing them the importance of cultural exchanges.

Another important issue is the training of teachers. To effectively teach topics related to intercultural communication, a teacher must have not only language skills, but also broad cultural knowledge and empathy skills. Regular training of teachers in this area and teaching new methods will increase their success in the learning process.

The resources and capabilities of the learning environment are also of great importance. For example, the availability of modern technologies, virtual communication platforms or materials for studying foreign cultures can significantly make the study of intercultural communication more effective. However, the lack of such resources often reduces the effectiveness of the process. This requires the active participation of educational institutions and governments in providing the necessary resources and cooperation.

Another part of the discussion is the results of intercultural dialogue. Through this process, students begin to understand their own cultural heritage more deeply. Getting acquainted with the traditions and values of other nations allows them to be tolerant not only abroad, but also towards their own compatriots. This contributes to strengthening peace and unity in society.

In general, the development of intercultural dialogue in the process of teaching English is not only a way for students to learn the language, but also an important step towards broadening their worldview, promoting cultural understanding and becoming successful individuals in modern society. Despite the difficulties encountered in this process, its importance is unlimited and it should be one of the priority areas of the education system.

Conclusion:

Intercultural dialogue is a bridge that connects humanity. It is not limited to language, but also provides an opportunity to understand, respect and live in harmony with other cultures. And teaching English is one of the most effective means of strengthening this bridge.

Through this process, students not only acquire linguistic knowledge, but also become active members of the global community. They learn the richness of different cultures, broaden their worldview, and at the same time, begin to

understand the importance of their own cultural heritage more deeply. This allows them to successfully integrate and communicate in modern society.

However, the difficulties and problems encountered along the way should not be ignored. Issues such as lack of motivation, the need to improve the skills of teachers, and limited resources can hinder this process. However, by finding ways to solve these problems, developing new methodological approaches, and effectively integrating them into the education system, this process can be made more effective.

In the future, educational institutions, educators, and society must work together to develop intercultural dialogue. This is of great importance not only for students, but also for the global community. After all, a generation that strives to understand each other and sees cultural differences as an asset will be able to resolve any complex situation peacefully and cooperatively.

Thus, the formation of intercultural communication skills in the process of teaching English is of great importance not only for education, but also for the sustainable and peaceful development of society. At each step of this process, we make a significant contribution to the formation of a more open, tolerant, and global society.

References:

1. Brown, H. Douglas. Principles of Language Learning and Teaching. Pearson Education, 2007.
2. Byram, M., & Zarate, G. Cultural Awareness and Language Learning. Cambridge University Press, 1997.
3. Hall, E. T. The Silent Language. Anchor Books, 1973.
4. Kramsch, C. Language and Culture. Oxford University Press, 1998.
5. Savielle-Troike, M. Introducing Second Language Acquisition. Cambridge University Press, 2006.
6. Tomalin, B., & Stempleski, S. Cultural Awareness. Oxford University Press, 1993.
7. Schumann, J. H. The Acculturation Model for Second Language Acquisition. University of California, 1978.
8. Lazar, I. Incorporating Intercultural Competence in Language Teacher Education. Council of Europe Publishing, 2003.
9. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Cambridge University Press, 2014.
10. Seelye, H. N. Teaching Culture: Strategies for Intercultural Communication. National Textbook Company, 1994.

11.Hofstede, G. Cultures and Organizations: Software of the Mind. McGraw-Hill Education, 2010.